

The Impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Disclosure on the Financial Performance of Pharmaceutical Companies

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Abstract

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) disclosure has gained prominence as stakeholders increasingly prioritise sustainable and ethical business practices. This study examines the impact of ESG performance on the financial outcomes of pharmaceutical companies, using Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) as financial performance indicators. The analysis focuses on panel data from the four largest UK-based pharmaceutical firms by market capitalisation over the period 2015 to 2023. Employing panel regression techniques, the study explores the relationship between ESG disclosure and financial performance. The results reveal a positive correlation between ESG and financial performance for AstraZeneca plc and Hikma plc across both metrics. Hutchmed plc demonstrates a positive relationship only when ROE is used, while GlaxoSmithKline plc exhibits a negative association with ESG across both financial indicators. Based on these findings, the study recommends that regulatory authorities mandate ESG investments to guide stakeholder decision-making and enhance transparency in sustainability reporting. Additionally, it advocates for a stakeholder-oriented ESG strategy that supports long-term value creation and promotes corporate sustainability.

Keywords: *Environmental, Social and Governance, Social Development Goals, Financial Performance, Pharmaceutical Companies.*

JEL Classification codes: *M14, G32, L65, G30, Q010.*

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Introduction

Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) is a structure that considers non-financial factors that will influence a company's future (IIMD, 2024). ESG consists of the environmental which may include climate change, biodiversity, pollution, water, waste, deforestation, and greenhouse

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gas emissions, social may include customer relations, human rights, occupational health and safety, employee relations, supply chain management and governance may include diversity, equity and inclusion, compensation, board management practices, corruption, regulatory compliance etc (Sustainalytics, 2022). It can be considered as a measure of risk management, non-financial performance, and management competence (Coelho et al, 2023; Boerner, 2011).

The story of ESG began in January 2004 when General Kofi Annan, former Secretary-General of the United Nations, wrote to more than 50 CEOs of major financial institutions to participate in a joint effort supported by the Swiss government and the International Finance Corporation (IFC). This joint effort was to integrate ESG into the capital markets, which later led to a report titled "Who Cares Wins" in 2005 (Forbes, 2018).

This report argued that integrating ESG components into capital markets will lead to an increase in societal outcomes and sustainable markets (Sustainalytics, 2022). The United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEPFI) also produced a report at the same time which highlighted a legal plan for the incorporation of ESG issues into institutional investment (Dathe et al, 2024; UNEPFI, 2005).

These reports made the United Nations establish Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI) as a benchmark for a sustainable global financial system. Since its existence in 2006, the members have increased from 63 to over 3,800 members which led the assets under management to increase from US\$6.5 trillion to US\$121 trillion (Forbes, 2018). PRI must foster ESG inclusion and decision-making through engagements and leadership (Forbes, 2018).

Over the past few years, investment in ESG has increased as investors, suppliers and consumers consider more than financial returns but also the company's compliance with the environment, society and quality of governance to avoid financial risk and distress exposure (Badayi et al, 2021). This focus has made ESG investment by institutions to be projected to soar 84% to US\$33.9 trillion in 2026 from US\$18.4 trillion in 2021 (PwC, 2022).

The public sector, especially central banks have announced their support in recent years to help in the transformation of financial systems. This involves incorporating ESG assessment and practices to measure the risks that may arise due to climate change and promoting the development of green finance (Dikau & Volz, 2018). Several initiatives were taken by the Central banks which include the Sustainable Banking Network and the Central Banks and Supervisors Network for Greening the Financial System (Dikau & Volz, 2021).

The pharmaceutical industry plays a vital role in policy relating to the study, discovery, and production of new drugs which help patients prevent and cure diseases, potentially increasing the livelihood of patients, which further contributes to the prosperity of the society at large (IFMA, 2022). This has made the industry contribute significantly to improvements in life expectancy and quality care, which relieve symptoms, prevent complications, and cure diseases (OECD, 2024).

Furthermore, this made the pharmaceutical industry in Europe adopt a strategy on November 25th, 2020, which is aimed at "ensuring access to affordable medicines, enhancing crisis preparedness and response mechanism, diversified and secure supply chains, supporting competitiveness, innovation and sustainability and ensuring a strong voice in the world by promoting high quality and safety standard" (European Commission, 2020).

ESG investment is growing at a faster pace in investors, institutions and stock exchanges are working closely to achieve long-term sustainability (Chen et al, 2023). The problem facing the pharmaceutical industry in incorporating ESG is balancing the provision of quality drugs to patients while ensuring profitability for the company. Hence, this poses a significant problem in achieving sustainability goals in the pharmaceutical industry. The research intends to investigate the effect

and outcome of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) on the financial performance of selected pharmaceutical companies.

Objectives

- i. Explore the drivers of implementing ESG in pharmaceutical companies using the literature.
- ii. Using the literature, explore the benefits of ESG implementation and its impact on the financial performance of pharmaceutical companies.

Methodology

The study uses quantitative data which was collected from a secondary method for various variables. This design helped examine the relationship between variables using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The main variables are return on assets, return on equity, and ESG rating while other explanatory variables include firm size, capex intensity, current ratio, leverage ratio, and EBIT to total revenue. This was followed by statistical evaluation measures which include descriptive statistics and regression analysis. This research design examined the impact of ESG disclosure on pharmaceutical financial performance between 2015 and 2023. The study adopted panel data regression. Thus, the panel data model is used to investigate the impact of ESG activities on financial performance and how this initiative has affected the default of companies.

To test the impact of ESG activities on financial performance, the following equation was used:

$$\frac{ROA}{ROE} = a_i + \beta_1 \cdot ESG \text{ Performance} + \beta_2 \cdot Capexintensity + \beta_3 \cdot Financial \text{ slack} + \beta_4 \cdot Firm \text{ size} + \beta_5 \cdot Leverage \text{ ratio} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Literature Review

Global Drivers of ESG

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) also known as Global Goals, have distinct goals that call for collaboration and action by all countries irrespective of class to foster prosperity while preserving the planet. Their goals align with putting an end to all forms of poverty which contributes significantly to economic growth and tackles social needs which include health, social protection, job opportunities, and education while addressing environmental protection and climate change (UN, 2020). They monitor countries progress on environmental, social and economic sustainability through 232 indicators which everyone which includes civil societies, businesses, researchers and government can access (UN, 2020).

SDG components align closely with ESG issues. Factors that influence both SDG success and ESG performance are similar, with SDG focus covering a wider range than ESG. Thus, SDG can be viewed as the intergovernmental version of ESG ideas (Daugaard & Ding, 2022).

Therefore, the drivers of ESG performance can be classified into four which include economic and social development, political and regulatory environment, financial market conditions and Socially Responsible Investment. The figure below shows the categories of activities that drives global ESG performance (Daugaard & Ding, 2022).

Figure 1. Categories of ESG Performance Drivers

A. Economic and Social Development: This involves creating public awareness coupled with corporate attention in increasing sustainability activities by firms and their disclosure has played a vital role in driving ESG performance over time (Xie et al, 2019).

B. Political and Regulatory Environment: Political systems such as legal framework and corruption drive ESG disclosure activities significantly (Baldini et al, 2018). Regulatory activities have over time influenced investors to factor ESG when making investment decisions (European Commission, 2018).

C. Financial Market conditions: The financial market conditions can serve as an avenue to drive ESG provided the market is in boom. This will motivate investors to invest or incorporate ESG activities to maximise this opportunity over time (Daugaard & Ding, 2022).

D. Socially Responsible Investment: is an approach which combines long-term financial gain for shareholders and non-financial return which promotes stakeholder’s interest which will ultimately drive ESG investments (Alsayegh et al, 2020).

The drivers of ESG are important as they take account of discussions and promotion of critical societal issues, policy implementation, and facilitation of community-oriented activities, with beneficial motivation and responsible and ecological effect which help expand the growth in ESG practices worldwide.

Industry Overview

The global pharmaceutical market (prescription) was estimated at \$1,287,736 million at ex-factory prices in 2022. The breakdown comprises of North American market (USA & Canada) recording 52.3% which has the largest share ahead of Europe, Africa, Asia, Australia, China, Japan and Latin America (EFPIA, 2023).

The industry continues to play a key role in the creation of new medicines and vaccines which are used by patients to prevent and treat diseases in the world. The success of the industry has been heavily reliant on continuous innovation to produce drugs and vaccines to tackle prevalent, complicated and overlooked diseases and technological advancement in current therapies and vaccinations (IFPMA, 2022).

BREAKDOWN OF THE WORLD PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET – 2022 SALES

Figure 2. Breakdown of the World Pharmaceutical Market (2022)

Source: EFPIA, 2023

Despite business conditions and regulatory standards faced in all sectors, the industry continues to invest in some of the riskiest tech areas which promotes medical research, widens the knowledge of science and boosts societal wealth. They continue to invest heavily in research and development of new vaccines and medicines which entails exploring chemical and biological substances which show capacity to treat current or recent ailments, or production of vaccines to provide antibiotics for an ailment (CDCP, 2020).

The biopharmaceutical industry has continuously made the highest investment in research and development even during economic uncertainty, recording about \$198 billion globally in research and development in 2020 (Pharma, 2021). The biopharmaceutical companies involved in innovation has made an investment of over a trillion dollars since 2015 (Pharma, 2021). This made the intensity of Research and investment by these companies account for 15.4% (Grassano et al, 2021).

Evidence of this intensity can be confirmed in Europe with 23 out of 50 leading worldwide R&D firms being biopharmaceutical companies in 2018 (Hernández, 2018). This further extended to 2019 where which research and development investment by biopharmaceutical and biotechnology sector increased by 10% compared to the last year reinforcing its position as the leader when it comes to investment in research and development (Grassano et al, 2021).

Based on the evidence shown above, it is obvious that the industry is now more concerned with ESG factors which closely align with the industry goal of creating drugs to increase patients' livelihood irrespective of regulatory standards, market dynamics, and competitive forces which all have an effect of profitability and risk management. This overview helps to evaluate the relevance of ESG variables related to other sector-specific components that affect financial performance.

Theoretical Review

Stakeholder Theory

The ideas of Freeman (1984) brought about the development of stakeholder theory and was further developed by other co-authors (e.g., Aydoğmuş et al, 2022, Chen & Xie, 2022; Freeman, 2010) which covers all aspects of the theory. Stakeholder theory postulates that firms can be seen as an array of relationships between stakeholders (Dmytriiev et al, 2021).

The main principle of stakeholder theory is that firms should generate value for all their stakeholders and these stakeholders may be different from one company to another depending on the company's business model. Generally, stakeholders may include customers, employees, suppliers, communities, bondholders, shareholders, and banks etc. (Dmytriiev et al, 2021). The theory highlights the significance of stakeholders which varies from one company to another and the impact they play in value creation for themselves and the firm at large.

Another important principle of the theory is the integration thesis. It posits that most businesses consider ethical content (Freeman et al, 2021; Freeman et al, 2010) and reject the fact that businesses should be separated from ethics cases (Gangi et al, 2019; Harris & Freeman, 2008). Stakeholder theory posits that businesses are part of the society rather than an independent entity. Therefore, business managers are not only responsible for profit maximization, debt minimization but also managing claims and minimizing harm within a complicated system of societal relationships (Wood et al, 2021). The theory considers everyone combining the business and ethical aspects together in its achievement of its goals.

The research is based on the stakeholder theory because this theory considers the relationship with the subject matter of this study. It specifies a link between the effect of ESG and the financial performance that the study examines.

Empirical Review

Studies have been carried out by various authors to explicitly show the nexus between ESG and financial performance while the focus of this study is on the pharmaceutical companies listed on FTSE 100, existing literature on the pharmaceutical industry and other economies, and industries was reviewed in the past five years.

Ahamd et al. (2021) re-examined the impact of ESG and financial performance of UK FTSE 350 companies. 351 samples were used between 2002 and 2018. The study used static and dynamic panel data techniques and its results show that there is a positive and significant impact between total ESG and firm financial performance, while highlighting that individual ESG performance results are mixed. The study also confirmed that high ESG companies have high financial performance compared to low ESG companies.

Ruan and Liu (2021) investigated the relationship between environmental, social, and governance (ESG) activities and firm performance in China, using data from 2015 to 2019. Based on a sample of companies listed on the Shanghai Stock Exchange and the A-share market, the study found that corporate ESG activities had a negative effect on firm performance.

Duque-Grisales and Aguilera-Caracuel (2021) analysed the relationship between environmental, social, and governance (ESG) scores and the financial performance of multinational firms operating in emerging Latin American markets. Using data from 104 multinationals between 2011 and 2015, their study revealed a statistically significant negative relationship between ESG scores and financial performance. When examining the environmental, social, and governance dimensions individually, each was also found to be negatively associated with firm performance.

This study contributed to the existing body of knowledge from various researchers on the impact of ESG disclosure on the financial performance of the pharmaceutical industry. Additionally, this study contributes significantly to limited literature, particularly in the pharmaceutical sector in the UK and will serve as foundational literature for future studies. Finally, the study will make a good recommendation on the effectiveness of ESG disclosure and its contribution to risk management and financial stability, potentially reducing financial risk and achieving stable financial performance.

Results and Discussion

The study describes the variables used in the study to analyse the impact of ESG on the financial performance of pharmaceutical companies in the UK. This gives a snapshot of data which describes the relationship between variables in a sample (Kaur et al, 2018). The data were analysed using inferential statistic.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Result

	AZN				GSK			
	Mean	S. D	Min.	Max.	Mean	S. D	Min	Max
ROA	3.92	1.88	0.13	6.03	8.63	6.68	1.62	21.48
ROE	14.33	6.95	0.41	22.23	62.23	52.25	29.24	179.63
ESG Perf	66.91	2.31	63.93	69.69	64.05	3.43	58.83	69.27
CAPEX	-1180.67	183.61	-1446.00	-961.00	-1301.11	187.56	-1545.00	-950.00
Fin. Slack	.93	0.12	0.80	1.16	.86	0.171	.60	1.24
Firm Size	4.46	0.13	4.34	4.66	4.47	.053	4.38	4.53
LR	89.27	23.18	59.29	123.60	228.21	158.62	96.39	552.04
EBIT	4171.44	1929.49	1077.00	8151.00	6139.56	2267.17	2651.00	10369.00
	HIK				HCM			
	Mean	S. D	Min	Max	Mean	S. D	Min	Max
ROA	4.82	10.48	-21.75	13.09	-10.39	13.64	-30.04	8.73
ROE	9.32	20.61	-43.12	25.57	-21.64	23.76	-57.15	15.03
ESG Perf	49.94	5.75	43.46	57.92	38.33	13.43	24.45	55.61
CAPEX	-129.00	29.82	-172.00	-82.00	-13.47	12.63	-36.66	-3.32
Fin Slack	1.81	.31	1.26	2.30	2.94	1.09	1.10	4.33
Firm Size	3.34	0.09	3.16	3.46	2.45	.21	2.25	2.92
LR	35.97	14.16	5.03	52.84	8.10	7.92	.00	26.17
EBIT	290.00	404.09	-747.00	582.00	-140.34	146.14	-407.69	18.38

Source: *Authors' calculations using SPSS*

From the Table 1 the data was divided into four firms, which are AstraZeneca plc (AZN), GlaxoSmithKline plc (GSK), Hikma plc (HIK) and Hutchmed plc (HCM). On average, the ESG rating for AZN equals 66.91, which is higher than the other three firms with GSK having an ESG rating of 64.05, HIK having ESG rating of 49.94 and HCM having an ESG rating of 38.33. Compared to other companies, HCM companies have, on average, negative values for profitability measures such as ROE and ROA. The debt-equity ratio (leverage) varies significantly within the sample of companies and is 228.21 percentage points for GSK, 89.37 percentage points for AZN, 35.97 percentage points for HIK and 8.10 percentage points for HCM. The current ratio (financial slack) might be considered good for all the firms and on average, AZN firms equal 0.93, GSK equal 0.86, HIK equals 1.81 and HCM equals 2.94, respectively.

On average, GSK's EBIT margin is higher than that of the other companies. It is 6139.56, AZN's is 4171.44, HIK's is 260.00 and HCM's is -140.34.

From the table analyzing the descriptive statistics of the sample, the study concludes that GSK company has better financial performance and higher ESG rating than the other three companies. In addition, their average debt-equity ratio is lower than 100%, except for GSK, which is higher than 100%.

Table 2. The Effect of ESG Performance on the Financial Performance of AstraZeneca and GlaxoSmithKline

AZN						
	ROA Beta (β)	ROE Beta (β)	ROASig.	ROE Sig	ROAR2	ROER2
Constant	-49.672	-102.738	0.620	.758	0.650	0.708
ESG Perf	.192	1.111	.852	.751		
CAPEX	-.012	-.037	.258	.288		
Fin Sla	-3.905	-14.171	.576	.551		
Firm size	5.359	-3.214	.845	.972		
LR	.075	.304	.533	.463		
GSK						
	ROA Beta (β)	ROE Beta (β)	ROASig.	ROE Sig	ROAR2	ROER2
Constant	-41.128	380.374	0.868	.797	0.660	0.803
ESG Perf	-1.620	-12.654	.409	.298		
CAPEX	.037	0.179	.262	.345		
Fin Sla	19.137	160.814	.449	.308		
Firm size	41.238	132.361	.513	.717		
LR	.004	-0.019	.855	.897		

Note: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 2 shows the effect of ESG performance on the financial performance of AstraZeneca company and GlaxoSmithKline company. The financial performance, which is ROA and ROE, was proxied as the independent variables.

For AstraZeneca, the econometric analysis of both the ROA and ROE models indicates a positive association between ESG performance and the company's financial outcomes. Specifically, the ROA model shows that a one-unit increase in ESG performance leads to a 0.192 percentage point rise in ROA. In this model, capital expenditure (capex) intensity and financial slack negatively influence financial performance, whereas firm size and leverage ratio exert a positive impact. Similarly, the ROE model reveals that a one-unit increase in ESG performance results in a 1.111 percentage point increase in ROE. However, in this case, capex intensity, financial slack, and firm size negatively affect performance, while the leverage ratio continues to show a positive contribution. The R^2 values for the ROA and ROE models are 0.650 and 0.708 respectively, suggesting a strong positive relationship between ESG performance and financial indicators.

In contrast, the findings for GlaxoSmithKline reveal a negative relationship between ESG performance and financial performance, as measured by both ROA and ROE. The ROA model suggests that a one-unit increase in ESG performance leads to a 1.62 percentage point decline in ROA. In this model, capex intensity, financial slack, firm size, and leverage ratio all positively influence performance. Meanwhile, the ROE model shows that a one-unit increase in ESG performance corresponds to a significant 12.654 percentage point drop in ROE. Here, capex intensity, financial slack, and firm size positively impact ROE, while leverage ratio has a negative effect. The R^2 values of 0.660 for ROA and 0.803 for ROE indicate that the models account for a substantial portion of the variation in financial performance with respect to ESG performance.

Table 3. The Effect of ESG Performance on the Financial Performance of Hikma and Hutchmed

	HIK					
	ROA Beta (β)	ROE Beta (β)	ROASig.	ROE Sig	ROAR ²	ROER ²
Constant	566.755	-1070662	0.328	.358	0.558	0.528
ESG Perf	2.953	5.636	.275	.300		
CAPEX	-0.116	-.209	.704	.736		
Fin Sla	-18.629	-36.333	.561	.577		
Firm size	200.353.	-378.103	.307	.338		
LR	-0.613	-1.173	.218	.240		
	HCM					
	ROA Beta (β)	ROE Beta (β)	ROASig.	ROESig	ROAR ²	ROER ²
Constant	-258.037	-383.615	0.004	.073	0.970	0.821
ESG Perf	-0.755	0.980	.047*	.251		
CAPEX	1.262	1.404	.032*	.206		
Fin Sla	-2.737	12.452	.419	.442		
Firm size	121.357	62.317	.004*	.047		
LR	.494	1.800	.533	.260		

Note: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 3 shows the effect of ESG performance on the financial performance of Hikma company and Hutchmed company. The financial performance, which is ROA and ROE, was proxied as the independent variables.

The econometric analysis of both ROA and ROE models for Hikma indicates a positive correlation between ESG performance and the company's financial outcomes. In the ROA model, a one-unit improvement in ESG performance is associated with a 2.953 percentage point increase in ROA. However, capital expenditure intensity, financial slack, and leverage ratio negatively impact the firm's performance, whereas firm size contributes positively. For the ROE model, a one-unit rise in ESG performance corresponds to a 5.636 percentage point increase in ROE. In this case, all control variables—capex intensity, financial slack, firm size, and leverage ratio—exert a negative influence on performance. The R² values for the ROA and ROE models are 0.558 and 0.528, respectively, indicating a moderately strong relationship between ESG activities and financial performance.

For Hutchmed, the ROA model results show a negative association between ESG performance and return on assets. Specifically, a one-unit increase in ESG performance leads to a 0.755 percentage point decline in ROA. Despite this, all control variables—firm size, capex intensity, financial slack, and leverage ratio—positively influence the firm's performance. Conversely, the ROE model reveals a positive relationship, with a one-unit increase in ESG performance resulting in a 0.980 percentage point rise in ROE. In this model, the same control variables also show a positive effect. The R² values are notably high: 0.970 for ROA and 0.821 for ROE, suggesting that the models provide a strong explanation of the variation in financial performance based on ESG performance.

Comparison of Results with Previous Findings

Based on the analysis, the study finds that there is a positive impact of ESG implementation on the financial performance of pharmaceutical companies. These results are in conformity with De Lucia et al. (2020), Aydoğmuş et al. (2022) and Chen et al. (2023). As evidenced by this study, this initiative serves as a risk mitigation technique for investors and stakeholders especially during

economic downturn confirmed by Fernández et al, (2019). This initiative also helps reduce capital costs, stock turnover and operational efficiencies (Whelan et al, 2021). The study also confirms a negative effect of ESG on financial performance which is in conformity with Agarwal et al. (2023), Martha & Khomsiyah, (2023) which establishes a negative effect between ESG and financial performance.

However, research has shown that there is a relationship between the financial performance of a company and its disclosure of ESG issues. Given that it promotes stable financial performance and lowers unsystematic risks, businesses should focus on integrating and maximising this initiative. Nevertheless, this initiative alone cannot drive financial performance of any company without other metrics which also is in conformity with Kim & Yoon, (2023).

Conclusions

This study examines the impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors on the financial performance of pharmaceutical companies in the United Kingdom over the period 2015 to 2023. It investigates how ESG-related activities influence corporate financial outcomes and offers recommendations on the role of ESG disclosure in enhancing risk management and financial stability. By potentially mitigating financial risks and supporting sustainable performance, ESG practices are particularly relevant to investors, corporate managers, and other stakeholders. The analysis relies on secondary data sourced from the Bloomberg Terminal. Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) are used as proxies for financial performance, while ESG performance is the main independent variable. Additional control variables include capital expenditure intensity, financial slack, firm size, leverage ratio, and EBIT as a proportion of total revenue.

The data analysis involved both descriptive statistics and panel data regression techniques. These methods provided a comprehensive view of the relationships between the selected variables and allowed for an evaluation of how firm-specific factors and extended time series influence financial outcomes, in line with the research objectives.

Panel data regression results varied across companies, which may reflect differences in headquarters locations, ESG investment strategies, reporting standards, market conditions, and firm-specific characteristics. While numerous studies have assessed ESG's impact on firm performance, this research offers a unique focus on the pharmaceutical sector—a relatively underexplored industry in this context. Unlike prior studies with a global or multi-sectoral scope, this research specifically targets UK-based pharmaceutical firms, adding valuable insights into regional ESG practices. Although the results are mixed—attributable to differences in regional contexts, ESG-related costs, and market environments—the findings provide important implications for ESG stakeholders in light of evolving market dynamics, geopolitical uncertainty, and climate-related challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this research, the following are recommended by this study.

1. Policymakers should make ESG practices mandatory as a requirement for all firms since it helps stakeholders, firm managers and investors formulate corporate strategies to make investment decisions thereby achieving value maximization and risk minimization.

2. Policymakers and international regulators should provide a framework which will help improve ESG disclosure and reporting standards thereby ensuring transparency and reliability which maximises shareholders' wealth.
3. There should be a comprehensive engagement strategy/communication with stakeholders to meet stakeholders' needs to drive sustainability.
4. Policymakers should implement financial procedures and incentives to increase the scale and reputation of ESG activities since its beneficial to stakeholders, the environment, and the planet.

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